

Deliverable D2.1 Dissemination Plan

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1	30/06/2025	First issue of Dissemination Plan
2	22/04/2026	Revised and updated the Dissemination to reflect current project status and dissemination practices.

Name	Details of contribution
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1 Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
ICSO	International Conference on Space Optics
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PIC	Photonic Integrated Circuit
RIF	Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation
UCY	University of Cyprus

2 Introduction

This Dissemination Plan outlines the strategy and actions for communicating and disseminating the results of the project “Photonic Integrated Circuit Self-Oscillating Comb for 6G”. The plan is developed and implemented by the University of Cyprus, the sole beneficiary of the project.

The main objective of dissemination activities is to ensure effective communication of the project’s progress and results to both the scientific community and the broader public, while safeguarding intellectual property and supporting future exploitation. This document defines the dissemination channels, target audiences, planned activities, and timelines, in alignment with the objectives of WP2.

3 Dissemination Objectives

The dissemination activities aim to:

- Promote awareness of the project goals and technological advancements,
- Maximize the visibility and impact of scientific results,
- Engage with both the academic community and the general public,
- Support future exploitation and funding opportunities,
- Ensure compliance with the requirements of the Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation.

4 Target Audiences

The dissemination strategy addresses multiple stakeholder groups:

- **Scientific Community:** Researchers and engineers in photonics, microwave photonics, and integrated optics,
- **Industry Stakeholders:** Companies active in photonic integration, telecommunications, and 6G technologies,
- **Policy Makers and Funding Bodies:** Including national and European research funding agencies,
- **General Public:** Through outreach and science communication activities.

5 Dissemination Channels and Activities

5.1 Scientific Publications and Conferences

Scientific dissemination will primarily be achieved through:

- Publications in high-impact journals (e.g. Journal of Lightwave Technology, Nature Photonics, Optics Express),
- Presentations at international conferences (e.g. Microwave Photonics, Photonics West, International Conference on Space Optics (ICSO) [1]).

During the initial phase of the project, one conference abstract has been submitted to the ICSO. Journal publications are planned for later stages of the project, following experimental validation of the system.

All publications will undergo internal review to ensure that intellectual property considerations are addressed prior to submission.

5.2 Online Presence and Digital Communication

A dedicated LinkedIn page has been established to communicate project updates, milestones, and achievements. This platform serves as the main digital dissemination channel, targeting both technical audiences and the wider public.

In addition, a project community has been created on Zenodo [2] to support open science practices, including data sharing, archiving, and long-term accessibility of project outputs.

5.3 Press Releases and Institutional Communication

Press releases constitute an important dissemination mechanism to reach the broader public and increase the visibility of the project at national and international level. These are coordinated through the communication channels of the University of Cyprus.

During the first phase of the project, one press release was issued to announce the official launch of the project. Additional press releases are planned at key milestones, such as PIC fabrication, experimental validation, and final results dissemination.

The indicative plan for press releases is presented below:

Milestone	Description	Timing
Project Launch	Announcement of project objectives and scope	Completed (2025)
PIC Fabrication	Announcement of successful fabrication and delivery of the PIC	Planned (2026)
Experimental Results	Communication of key scientific and technical achievements	Planned (2026–2027)
Project Completion	Summary of outcomes and impact	Planned (2027)

5.4 Outreach and Public Engagement

The project aims to engage with the public through participation in outreach activities such as the European Researchers' Night [3].

Due to resource constraints, participation in the 2025 edition was not feasible. However, participation is planned for future editions, ensuring alignment with the project's dissemination objectives and increased public engagement.

5.5 Networking and Collaboration Activities

Dissemination is further supported through networking and collaboration initiatives, including:

- Participation in proposal consortia and European research programmes,
- Engagement with academic and industrial partners.

In this context, two Horizon Europe proposals were submitted during the reporting period, strengthening the project's visibility and integration within the European research ecosystem.

6 Intellectual Property and Dissemination Control

All dissemination activities are aligned with the project's IPR Management and Exploitation Plan. Prior to any public disclosure, results are reviewed to ensure that:

- Potential intellectual property is protected,
- Opportunities for commercialization are preserved.

This controlled dissemination approach ensures a balance between openness and exploitation potential.

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

Dissemination activities will be continuously monitored using both qualitative and quantitative indicators, including:

- Number of publications and conference contributions,
- Online engagement metrics (e.g. LinkedIn activity),
- Participation in outreach events,
- Involvement in collaborative projects and proposals.

Adjustments to the dissemination strategy will be made as necessary to maximize impact.

8 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

To ensure effective monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities, a set of quantitative Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been defined. These indicators will be used to track progress and assess the impact of dissemination actions throughout the project duration.

Category	Activity	KPI Target	Status (Year 1)
Scientific Dissemination	Conference Contributions	≥ 2 submissions	1 submitted (ICSO)
Scientific Dissemination	Journal Publications	≥ 2 publications	Planned (post-experimental phase)
Digital Communication	LinkedIn Posts	≥ 5 posts	Ongoing
Digital Communication	Online Presence (followers/engagement)	Continuous growth	Established
Open Science	Zenodo Community	1 established community	Completed

Public Outreach	Participation in Researchers' Night	≥ 1 participation	Planned
Press & Media	Press Releases	$\geq 3-4$ releases	1 completed
Networking	Horizon Europe Proposals	≥ 2 submissions	2 submitted
Exploitation Support	IPR-related outputs	Continuous monitoring	Ongoing

9 Conclusions

The dissemination activities during the first phase of the project have focused on establishing the necessary communication infrastructure and initiating engagement with the scientific community. Key foundations, including online presence and data management practices, have been successfully implemented.

Future dissemination efforts will intensify following the availability of experimental results, with an emphasis on high-impact publications, conference participation, and public outreach. The structured and adaptive dissemination strategy ensures that the project will achieve strong visibility, scientific impact, and exploitation potential.

10 References

- [1] International Conference on Space Optics (ICSO). [Online]. Available: <https://www.icso2024.org>
- [2] Zenodo – General-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN.
- [3] European Researchers' Night, European Commission. [Online]. Available: <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu>